

thanks to the **LiquidO consortium**...

L I Q U I D

Detection and Imaging in Opaque Media

Neutrino Seminar @ FNAL

4th May 2023 — Chicago, USA

Université de Paris

Anatael Cabrera

CNRS/IN2P3

IJCLab/Université Paris-Saclay

(Orsay)

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AGENCE NATIONALE DE LA RECHERCHE

L I Q U I D O

LiquidO: light detector with **opaque** medium
⇒ event-wise **imaging**⊕**topology** & **PID** (high doping scenario)

what's LiquidO?

LiquidO Consortium*

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invention/conception 2012-2013 — since 2016 consortium (~20 institutes & 10 countries)

Anatael Cabrera (CNRS-IN2P3) — IJCLab / Université Paris-Saclay (Orsay)

4 today's liquid scintillator technology: transparent...

extremely low overburden → new technology needed

CTF @ Gran Sasso
(Borexino R&D)

the art of building images (2D)...

placing **point**(s) [confined information] in **space** [2D]

each energy deposition...

- **points** $3D(x,y,z)$ & **energy** $1D(E)$
⇒ **lines** (i.e. point-sequence)

- **time** $1D(t)$ — optional (generally available)

“**energy-flow**” → **energy-points** ordered in **time**

(dynamic) **imaging** building-blocks...

stochastic light confinement

LiquidO → photon's "random walk" (self-confinement)

- **scattering** → **random walk** → **light ball** [order 1 cm]
 - scattering mean-free-path order 1mm: $\times 10^{-4}$ smaller than usual
 - **lossless (elastic) light scattering:**
 - **Mie scattering:** achromatic & tiny losses ["cloudy" touch]
 - **Rayleigh scattering:** chromatic & lossless
 - **Internal Reflection** (Snell's law lossless)
- warning:** avoid reflection (losses @ order $\sim 1\%$ /reflection)

LiquidO ⇔ **unique stochastic light confinement**
⇒ **must NOT be transparent!!**

Transparency
 $\lambda(\text{scattering}) \geq 10\text{m}$

Rayleigh & Mie Scattering
 $\lambda(\text{scattering}) \leq 1\text{cm}$

inducing light to a point (lossless)...

Topology (X,Y) direct & native (PID) → possible mm vertex precision

Simplest LiquidO: 1D lattice (fibres along Z-axis only) — axial configuration

TOP VIEW: (X,Y) Projection → readout TOP

e+ annihilation

Z position using: Δt (time difference)

BOTTOM VIEW: (X,Y) Projection → readout BOTTOM

opaque medium → stochastic light confinement (self-segmentation)

LiquidO: sub-nuclear MeV imaging...

opaque medium \rightarrow stochastic light confinement
(**self-segmentation**)

novel LiquidO engineering...

LiquidO axial-fibres “parallel”

LiquidO axial-fibres “crossed”

I Q U I D

1x Axis(Z) — low cost & simplicity

- (X,Y): topology → **mm resolution** (robust)
- Z: timing → **few cm resolution** → some fragility: light yield, rise-time, etc

2x Axes — complexity & cost...

- (X,Y,Z): topology → **mm resolution** (robust)
- (X,Y,Z): timing → cheap-readout / over-constrained

3x Axes — useless?

“1x” Axis (twisted-Z @ $\leq 10^\circ$) — development

- (X,Y): topology → **mm resolution** (robust)
- Z: topology → **≤ 1 cm resolution** (robust)
- (X,Y,Z): timing → over-constrain & **energy-flow**

more Axes: necessary?

main technological ingredients...

full engineering for "floating fibres"

sub-100ps custom front-end & digitisation

LiquidO Front-End (SiPM)

WaveCatcher & SAMPIC

SiPM @Hamamatsu S13 (so far)

new scintillation & fibres technologies
(Cherenkov / scintillation / etc)

fast readout ⊕ reconstruction
(potential resolution ≤ 100 ps)

new framework for light detection → several new ideas...

scintillator ✓ (Borexino et al)

⊕

fibres ✓? (R&D)
(counting $\sim 10^{-12}$ g/g U/Th)

⊕

photo-detector ✓ (SiPM / no PMT / distance)

⊕

adding anything else?

new opaque scintillators

LiquidO's R&D (new projects...)

“Mycro-Crystal Scintillator”

S. Wagner, M. Grassi, A. Cabrera

[arXiv:1807.00628](https://arxiv.org/abs/1807.00628)

liquid scintillator(s)

(optional)

⊕

μCrystal inorganic scintillator(s)

(doping)

emulsion (milk / mayonnaise)

liquid easy scattering — cheap & free

μCrystals possible too — exploring...

nano stuff possible — extremely expensive: practical?

opaque scintillation — a new technology

LiquidO R&D (prototypes now)

“NOWaSH”

First Opaque Scintillator @MPIK
[arXiv:1908.03334](https://arxiv.org/abs/1908.03334)

“amorphous WAX-based”
[prototyping: tune scattering with Temperature]

$\approx 0.1 \text{ MeV}$

topology	physics	LiquidO Information	
point	unresolved (\lesssim few cm)	point-like	sub-mm possible (primitive)
track	points-like sequence	track-like	sub-mm possible (enhanced)
point's \oplus track's	complex event	combination \oplus timing	reconstruction (energy \oplus x,y,z \oplus t)

input **5D** \rightarrow **energy-flow, kinematics** (\vec{p}), **PID**, etc (derived)

imaging & outcome (upon reco)...

beyond native capability...?

why going beyond native composition?

organic scintillator = H + ^{12}C + $^{12}\text{C}(\sim 1\%)$ [+ impurities]

**detection efficiency
enhancement**

**neutrino interaction(s)
enhancement**

**rare decay source
enhancement**

Evaluated at 30 MeV

Cd loading
[Reines et al]

Gd/Li loading
[typical in reactors]

$\beta\beta$ decay
 ^{136}Xe [KamLAND-Zen]
 ^{130}Te [SNO+]

≥ 10 tons $\beta\beta$?

the power of coincidences

low energy ($\leq 3\text{MeV}$) neutrinos interactions benefit by interactions leading to coincidences

Reines et al 1956

(neutrino discovery)

Raghavan et al 1977

(pp solar neutrino — unobserved)

major **R&D** by **LENS** *et al* [many years]

isotopic mass: loading vs enrichment...

isotopic loading (% or kg/kg^{LS})

isotopic fraction (abundance)

$m^{iso}(\text{ton})$ [V=1000m ³]	0.1 1g/l	0.5 5g/l	1.0 10g/l	5.0 50g/l	10.0 100g/l	50.0 250g/l	100.0 1000g/l
1.0	0.01	0.05	0.09	0.5	0.9	4.5	9.0
5.0	0.05	0.23	0.5	2.3	4.5	22.5	45.0
10.0	0.09	0.5	0.9	4.5	9.0	45.0	90.0
33.0	0.3	1.5	3.0	14.9	29.7	148.5	297.0
90.0 enriched	0.8	4.1	8.1	40.5	81.0	405.0	810.0

≈ 1.0ton
≥ 1.0ton

↓
today
reactor

↓
SNO+

↓
LENS & SNO+
R&D (done)

→ **new
R&D?**

massive loading capability (**R&D**) ⇒ **no enrichment!**

enrichment costing: [10, 100]M€/ton

doping stability via solidification...

(beyond chemical stability)

L I Q U I D O

physics appetiser... (simulation)

unprecedented PID@MeV...

potential: reduce overburden/shielding

opacity → (native) self-segmentation

needless segmentation: problematic @ 1MeV (pollution, cost ⊕ complex, etc)

reduce (eliminate) overburden?

lesson: avoid (if possible) civil construction...

neutrino excavations now...

complementary physics beyond deep underground?

multi-MeV improves (more light too)...

- **powerful PID**
- **energy flow**
- **tracking (mm)**
→ cosmogenic BG tagging
- **directionality**
- **dE/dx (range)**

~10MeV: D@R (μ, π, K), supernovae (remnant, core-collapse), atmospheric, Michel- e^\pm (μ -decay), etc

complex GeV with LiquidO...

Stochastic calorimetry order 0.1% [$\sim 10^5$ PE/GeV] — excellent control of non-stochastic

≥ 100 MeV: accelerator, atmospheric, p-decay, etc

energy flow: EM evolution of energy in time

discovery channels too...

$m(\text{proton}) \sim 1 \text{ GeV}$

free-H per unit of mass:
water: $\sim 10\%$
scintillator: up to 20%

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experimental demonstration (data)

nature communications physics

[nature](#) > [communications physics](#) > [articles](#) > [article](#)

Article | [Open Access](#) | [Published: 21 December 2021](#)

Neutrino physics with an opaque detector

[LiquidO Consortium](#)

[Communications Physics](#) **4**, Article number: 273 (2021) | [Cite this article](#)

4251 Accesses | **6** Citations | **23** Altmetric | [Metrics](#)

Abstract

In 1956 Reines & Cowan discovered the neutrino using a liquid scintillator detector. The neutrinos interacted with the scintillator, producing light that propagated across transparent volumes to surrounding photo-sensors. This approach has remained one of the most widespread and successful neutrino detection technologies used since. This article introduces a concept that breaks with the conventional paradigm of transparency by confining and collecting light near its creation point with an opaque scintillator and a dense array of optical fibres. This technique, called LiquidO, can provide high-resolution imaging to enable efficient identification of individual particles event-by-event. A natural affinity for adding dopants at high concentrations is provided by the use of an opaque medium. With these and other capabilities, the potential of our detector concept to unlock opportunities in neutrino physics is presented here, alongside the results of the first experimental validation.

In the top 25% of all research outputs scored by Altmetric

High Attention Score compared to outputs of the same age (92nd percentile)

High Attention Score compared to outputs of the same age and source (88th percentile)

proof-of-concept: *simulation & data* [**μ -LiquidO** prototype]

neutrino physics potential — appetiser

www.nature.com/articles/s42005-021-00763-5

LiquidO's prototype MINI-II (upgrade)

data taking since 2021

overall view

3" PMT
(test transparency)

64 channels readout
(pitch $\xi \approx 1.5\text{cm}$)

single electrons
[0.4, 1.8] MeV mono-energetic

~10L multi-media

- water (transparent)
- scintillator (transparent)
- scintillator (transparent ↔ opaque)

top view

T control
radiator ⊕ chiller: [5, 40] °C

Water: single e⁻ Cherenkov only

little light: Cherenkov only & transparent (LiquidO's lowest acceptance)

→ validate detector's integral timing readout — dominated by fibre's excitation?

LAB: Scintillation ⊕ Cherenkov

~8.7x more light due to native LAB's scintillation
 [adding fluors such as PPO ($\leq 3\text{g/L}$) \rightarrow increase further **~4x more**]

Cherenkov excites the scintillator — loss $\geq 50\%$ (\rightarrow optimisation)

Cherenkov time-only ID — threshold

(no topology exploited — unlike μ 's)

huge scattering
→ spread light!

ANY light detection: Cherenkov / Scintillation / anything!
(ensure the opaque medium is granted)

NW@40°: Scintillation ⊕ Cherenkov

“NW” = NoWaSH scintillator

“transparent” — effectively like LAB or Water

more light? scattering enhances fibre's collection → translucent regime

Cherenkov reduced by paraffine? — under investigation

“NW” = NoWaSH opaque scintillator (our prototype scintillator)

LiquidO (Opaque Scintillation)

Light Ball
more light
(≥80% in few cm)

light falls by almost 4 orders of magnitude in 20cm — very opaque indeed

raw data (no ToF, etc corrections)

more light thanks to LiquidO's aggressive scattering...

- faster collection & better light containment
- formation **topology** → **stochastic light confinement** → LiquidO

self-segmentation → lossless light scattering [data → **negligible losses?**]

opacity metamorphosis...

light yield exploration...

LiquidO: ~80% light collected within 5 cm's

brightest while light falls by almost 4 orders of magnitude in 20cm

effective detected light yield > 120PE/MeV [@ SiPM]

≥250PE/MeV — **optimisation** (ongoing engineering)

LiquidO's Duality: lightness & darkness coexist

“one is cause/consequence of the other”

Geant4 Simulation (under tuning)

“light ball” size:

- scattering: λ_s
- # fibres
- absorption?

✓ **LiquidO: light/opacity → stochastic light confinement** ✓

any source (Cherenkov / scintillation / any light) ✓

any media (liquid / solid / (impractical?) gas?) ✓

✓ **doping:** a powerful (optional) “byproduct”

new technology: **opaque scintillation...** ✓

LiquidO's official website...

<https://liquidoin2p3.fr/>

on behalf of the **LiquidO consortium...**

L I Q U I D O

XXX Neutrino Conference
June 2022 — Seoul, South Korea

Anatael Cabrera
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(Orsay)

European Innovation Council

ANR

IJCLab
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CNRS universit PARIS-SACLAY FACULT DES SCIENCES D'ORSAY Universit de Paris

<https://neutrino2022.org>

LiquidO's MINI- γ Prototype...

for even more info, please see the **neutrino side...**

topology's PID (no timing)...

MINI's light ball →
 ~80% light within ≈4cm (radius) @1.8MeV

← normally ($r \geq 30\text{cm} \Leftrightarrow \geq 1.5\text{ns}$ for σ^{PMT})

← normally here: **NO e/gamma PID**

Doping Impact
 optimisation **PID vs doping**
 (5 orders of magnitude)

LiquidO: light detector with **opaque** medium

[*stochastic light confinement* → **imaging** ⊕ topology & **PID**]

LiquidO (5D primitive imaging info)

L I Q U I D O

light-based “**TPC**” (highest duty-cycle)

⊕

uniform calorimeter (scintillation)

⊕

Time-of-Flight (4π acceptance)

⊕

imaging (PID, energy-flow, magnetisable, etc)

⊕

doping (variable composition/density & more physics)

physics?

L I Q U I D

tightly linked to **LiquidO**, **AM-OTech/CLOUD**, and **SuperChooz** collaborations/consortia & specially **EDF**

The poster features the word "SUPERCHOOZ" in large, spaced-out letters at the top. Below it, the European Innovation Council logo is displayed. A central box indicates the "Seminar @ CERN" taking place in November 2022 in Geneva, Switzerland, featuring Anatael Cabrera from IJCLab (Orsay) and CNRS / Université Paris-Saclay. Logos for IJCLab, Université Paris-Saclay, Université de Paris, CNRS, and EDF are also present.

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.7504162](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7504162)

<https://zenodo.org/record/7504162>

SuperChooz just released...

S U P E R C H O O Z

exploration European flagship physics...

SuperChooz experimental site...

Antineutrino Reactor (@1.1km):

- $\phi \approx 6 \text{ v}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}\cdot\text{ton}^{-1}$ [\rightarrow **DC-FD**]
- $\phi \approx 20\text{M v}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$ [\sim **10kton**]
- $\phi \approx$ **220M v's** [exposure: 100,000 ton \cdot year]

Neutrinos Sun:

- $\phi_{\odot} \approx$ **2.5e5 v's** [exposure: 100,000 ton \cdot years]

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UK Research
and Innovation

AM-OTech project [EIC-UKRI]
CLOUD experiment

1 Dec 2022

Chooz-B: Reactor Cores

Chooz-A: Cavern Reactor Core

Ultra Near Detectors @ Chooz-B:

- LiquidO technology
- Mass: ≤ 5 tons
- Overburden: $\leq 5\text{m}$
- Baseline: $\leq 30\text{m}$

Super Far Detector @ Chooz-A

- LiquidO technology
- Mass: $\sim 10,000$ tons
- Overburden: $\leq 100\text{m}$
- Baseline: $\sim 1\text{km}$

Antineutrino Reactor (@20m):

- $\phi \approx 16\text{k v}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}\cdot\text{ton}^{-1}$ [\rightarrow **DC-ND**]
- $\phi \approx 10\text{M v}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$ [\sim **2ton**]
- $\phi \approx$ **100M v's** [exposure: 20 ton \cdot year]

Neutrinos Sun:

- $\phi_{\odot} \leq$ **100 v's** [exposure: 20 ton \cdot years]

neutrinos in Europe?

powerful synergies **JUNO** ⊕ **HyperK** ⊕ **DUNE** — after all running!

experimental demonstration...

a priori no showstopper

SuperChooz : ~9 700 m³

some **common technology** but **not methodology**

- scintillator: ✓ (improvement)
- fibres ✓ (improvement)
- segmentation ✗ (simplification, cheaper, less BG)
- light collection: ✓ (improvement expected)
- photo-detector: ✓ (simplification with SiPM)
- MeV optimisation → **Scaling R&D [≥2024]**

SuperChooz (~10kton) similar dimensions as **NOvA (~14kton)** & one module of **DUNE (~10kton)**

2 - 4 November 2022
Valencia

DUNE Module of Opportunity Workshop

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REGISTRATION OPEN UNTIL OCT 25: [Register](#)

Preliminary agenda now available

You can check it [here](#)

The abstract submission closed on Oct 6th

DUNE Module of Opportunity Open Workshop

The DUNE experiment consists of four 17 kton liquid-argon far detector modules in separate cryostats. The technology choices for the first two modules have been established and are being implemented as part of the experiment's Phase I. The third and fourth modules will complete the DUNE Far Detector. These modules provide opportunity for further development of liquid-argon or alternate detector technologies in support of the DUNE physics goals.

The DUNE Collaboration invites the broader particle physics community to participate in this OPEN WORKSHOP (DUNE collaboration membership not required) to explore options for expanded physics opportunities and novel detector technologies for these "modules of opportunity" that will be part of DUNE's Phase II. The meeting will address how to improve the DUNE's primary physics program and how to broaden the physics scope of the experiment. The meeting will cover all major aspects of liquid argon TPC technology, including proposals for improvements in tracking, photon detection, electronics, high voltage, electronics and data-acquisition, considering improvements in detector integration, installation and background reduction. New detector concepts that can satisfy and expand the DUNE physics goals are also encouraged.

This is the second edition of this workshop series. The first edition was held at BNL (USA) in November 2019: <https://www.bnl.gov/dmo2019/>

This Workshop is sponsored by:

possible support to DUNE?

the first LiquidO experiment...

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first international release : very soon!!

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C L O U D

**Innovation Programme (confidential for now) — “Antimatter-OTech”
Fundamental Science Programme (soon)**

 EDF (France) — **first time in neutrinos!**

- **CIEMAT** (Spain)
- **IJCLab/Université Paris-Saclay** (France)
- **J-G Universität Mainz** (Germany)
- **Subatech/Nantes Université** (France)
- **Sussex University** (UK)

-
- **Charles University** (Czech Republic)
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 - **University of Zaragoza** (Spain)
 - **Tohoku University / RCNS** (Japan)
 - **Brookhaven National Laboratory** (USA)
 - **Michigan University** (USA)
 - **Pennsylvania State University** (USA)

CLOUD collaboration (EDF ⊕ 16 institutions over 10 countries)

the Ardennes mountains

the Meuse river

neutrino emission: $\sim 10^{21}$ ν /s per core

CLOUD Detector

- **LiquidO** technology
- Mass: \sim **5ton**
- Overburden: \leq **3m**
- Baseline: \leq **30m (UND)**
- **Rate: \geq 10,000 ν per day**

$\Rightarrow \delta[\phi_{\text{reactor}}] \approx 1\%$ (day) — world's best precision [DC]

Chooz-B: Reactor Cores

experimental setup...

ultra-near site @ Chooz...

nature
physics

ARTICLE
First Double Chooz θ_{13} Measurement via Total Neutron Capture Detection

Double Chooz @ 400m → CLOUD @ ~30m

3rd generation of neutrino science @ Chooz — Europe's most powerful reactor neutrino laboratory

C L O U D

European
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UK Research
and Innovation

funded & preparing construction...

physics!!

L I Q U I D

Дякую...
thanks...
danke...
고맙습니다...
merci...
ありがとう...
obrigado...
спасибі...
grazie...
谢谢...
hvala...
gracias...
شكرا...

L I Q U I D

<https://liquido.ijclab.in2p3.fr/>

LiquidO — foreseen performance **proved** → **optimisation!!** (first experiments **funded** → **imminent construction**)

- **how far? data suggest still more...** [publications soon]
- **robust & rich detection framework** — **sub-atomic topology imaging** (PID) / **mm vertex** / **doping**, etc
- **R&D** (still): **enhance & specialise performance** — ex. **new opaque scintillators!**
- **CLOUD/AntiMatter-OTech**: fundamental science physics programme [**publication soon**] → **SuperChooz** one day?